

Zybert Golden Correlations

After many simulations I noticed that many ZC Zybertsphere parameters had linear log-log correlations, and mostly $R^2 = 1$ or ≈ 1 . And when graphing data, I realised that log-log plots were far more convenient, indeed, some simulation parameters and equations were already logarithms such as $\textcircled{Z}T$ and $\textcircled{Z}M$. Also, $\textcircled{Z}Z$ vs $\textcircled{Z}T$ involved previously measured parameters (i.e. H_0), and since $\textcircled{Z}Z$ vs $\textcircled{Z}T$ was linear I wondered what other ZC parameters had linear correlations, especially measurable ones.

A $Z_m = E3 | Z_a = 20$ Zybertsphere, of $\textcircled{Z}T.N2 = E8 | \Delta T = E-4 | IC = E-18$, was simulated up to $\textcircled{Z}T = E20y$, and the log-log correlations are in Table 1a. In Table 1a, and 1b, the data is the Coefficient of Determination R^2 , and all parameters in Table 1a have linear correlations with $R^2 \geq 0.9995$. When $\Delta T = E-5$ R^2 is similar. Table 1b shows correlations for $Z_m = E3 : E5 | Z_a = 1 : 200$ Zybertspheres, with $\textcircled{Z}T.N2 = E8 | \Delta T = E-4 | IC = E-18$. Some Zybertspheres within this group were excluded if they were unviable e.g. $\textcircled{Z}M <$ our visible sphere, or if viable distorted correlations to $R^2 < 0.9$, usually for $Z_a < 10$. The parameters correlated are those when the Zybert Parameter $\textcircled{Z}Z = 7E4$ for each Zybertsphere. It seems parameters have an affinity for either (mainly) geometry or time, compare row $\textcircled{Z}R$ with $\textcircled{Z}T$.

Correlations which are common to Table 1a and 1b are in darker green, and there seems to be many universal linear log-log correlations between parameters of individual and grouped Zybertspheres. But 21 correlations being linear for individual Zybertspheres (during their evolution) were exponential or logarithmic for grouped Zybertspheres (at $\textcircled{Z}Z = 7E4$), indicated by * in Table 1b. And also in Table 1b $\textcircled{Z}\rho \approx \pm 1E-26$, and did correlate, as order 4 polynomials. Correlations with $R^2 < 0.99$ are in light red.

Table 1a. Correlations of \textcircled{Z} parameters for a $Z_m = E3 | Z_a = 20$ Zybertsphere during evolution

Table 1b. Correlations of \textcircled{Z} parameters for $Z_m = E3 : E5 | Z_a = 10 : 200$ Zybertspheres at $\textcircled{Z}Z = 7E4$

	$\textcircled{Z}M$	$\textcircled{Z}R$	$\textcircled{Z}V$	$\textcircled{Z}A$	$\textcircled{Z}A'$	$\Delta\textcircled{Z}A'/\Delta T$	$\Delta\textcircled{Z}A'/\Delta R$	$\Delta\textcircled{Z}Z/\Delta\textcircled{Z}T$	$\Delta\textcircled{Z}Z/\Delta\textcircled{Z}R$	$\textcircled{Z}\rho$
$\textcircled{Z}M$		1	1	1	0.9997	0.9997	1	0.9997	1	0.9997
$\textcircled{Z}R$	1		1	1	0.9996	0.9996	1	0.9997	1	0.9997
$\textcircled{Z}T$	0.9996	0.9996	0.9996	0.9995	1	1	0.9997	1	0.9997	1
$\Delta\textcircled{Z}Z/\Delta\textcircled{Z}T$	0.9997	0.9997	0.9996	0.9996	1	1	0.9997		0.9997	1
$\Delta\textcircled{Z}Z/\Delta\textcircled{Z}R$	1	1	1	1	0.9997	0.9997	1	0.9997		0.9998

	$\textcircled{Z}M$	$\textcircled{Z}R$	$\textcircled{Z}V$	$\textcircled{Z}A$	$\textcircled{Z}A'$	$\Delta\textcircled{Z}A'/\Delta T$	$\Delta\textcircled{Z}A'/\Delta R$	$\Delta\textcircled{Z}Z/\Delta\textcircled{Z}T$	$\Delta\textcircled{Z}Z/\Delta\textcircled{Z}R$	$\textcircled{Z}\rho$
$\textcircled{Z}M$		1	1	1	*0.9258	*0.9987	1	*0.9987	1	0.9984
$\textcircled{Z}R$	1		1	1	*0.9253	*0.9991	1	*0.9991	1	0.9984
$\textcircled{Z}T$	*0.9987	*0.9991	*0.9471	*0.9707	0.9583	0.9627	*0.9945	0.9993	*0.9972	0.9981
$\Delta\textcircled{Z}Z/\Delta\textcircled{Z}T$	*0.9987	*0.9991	*0.9404	*0.9654	0.9594	0.9641	*0.9944		*0.9972	0.9681
$\Delta\textcircled{Z}Z/\Delta\textcircled{Z}R$	1	1	1	1	*0.9279	*0.9972	1	*0.9972		0.9984

Table 2 is a set of simulations of $Z_m=E3:E5 | Z_a=20:160$ Zybetspheres, $\textcircled{Z}T.N2=E8 | \Delta T=E-4 | IC=-18$ and the data displayed are logarithms and sorted by $\textcircled{Z}M$ (or $\textcircled{Z}T$ or $\textcircled{Z}R$).

Table 2. $Z_m=E3:E5 | Z_a=20:160$ Zybetspheres (with $\textcircled{Z}T$ in years and parameters are for $N2$)

Z_m	Z_a	IC	$\textcircled{Z}T$	$\textcircled{Z}M$	$\textcircled{Z}R$	$\textcircled{Z}Z$	$\textcircled{Z}\rho$	$\textcircled{Z}A'$	$\textcircled{Z}\dot{Z}$	$\Delta\textcircled{Z}A'/\Delta\textcircled{Z}T$	$\Delta\textcircled{Z}Z/\Delta\textcircled{Z}R$	$\Delta\textcircled{Z}A'/\Delta\textcircled{Z}R$
E3	160	-18	9.99	23	10	4.8500	-25.2900	-16.6039	-5.1453	-26.8151	-5.4750	-27.1453
E3	80	-18	10.46	85	31	4.8500	-25.5100	-16.8197	-5.6208	-27.2923	-26.2810	-47.9523
E3	40	-18	10.92	242	83	4.8500	-25.6100	-16.9247	-6.0820	-27.7533	-79.1450	-100.8143
E4	160	-18	11.15	508	172	4.8500	-25.6400	-16.9507	-6.3044	-27.9773	-167.8303	-189.4996
E3	20	-18	11.36	678	228	4.8500	-25.6600	-16.9677	-6.5131	-28.1853	-224.6847	-246.3569
E4	80	-18	11.53	1166	391	4.8500	-25.6700	-16.9777	-6.6863	-28.3593	-387.5213	-409.1936
E4	40	-18	11.95	2861	956	4.8500	-25.6900	-16.9987	-7.1136	-28.7863	-953.0844	-974.7556
E5	160	-18	12.16	5636	1881	4.8500	-25.7000	-17.0117	-7.3210	-28.9933	-1878.2610	-1899.9583
E4	20	-18	12.37	7522	2510	4.8500	-25.7200	-17.0287	-7.5215	-29.1933	-2507.0414	-2528.7156
E5	80	-18	12.54	12647	4218	4.8500	-25.7400	-17.0497	-7.6984	-29.3703	-4215.6524	-4237.3276
E5	40	-18	12.97	30839	10282	4.8500	-25.8400	-17.1527	-8.1247	-29.7963	-10279.9710	-10301.6453
E5	20	-18	13.36	80430	26813	4.8500	-26.0900	-17.3977	-8.5154	-30.1873	-26810.8564	-26832.5336

Notice how uniformly all parameters change, how $\textcircled{Z}\rho$ decreases uniformly from $5.13E-26$ to $0.81E-26$. Notice how the age of Zybetspheres i.e. $\textcircled{Z}T$ when $\textcircled{Z}Z=7E4$, increases with increasing $\textcircled{Z}M$, uniformly. Notice how $\textcircled{Z}A'$ and $\textcircled{Z}\dot{Z}$ decrease as $\textcircled{Z}T$ increases but $\textcircled{Z}Z$ is constant at the value in our visible sphere. Notice how the $Z_m=E3 | Z_a=160$ Zybetsphere has $\textcircled{Z}T=E9.99$ whilst the $Z_m=E5 | Z_a=20$ has $\textcircled{Z}T=E13.36$ – a relatively narrow age range for such vastly different Zybetspheres.

Notice that this elegant uniformity applies to the smallest Zybetspheres e.g. $Z_m=E3 | Z_a=160$ which at $E23kg$ is a microZybetsphere, $7.83E-31$ times the mass of our visible sphere, $1.7E-20$ times our galaxy and yet it is just as viable a Zybetsphere as the largest e.g. $Z_m=E5 | Z_a=20$ being a macroZybetsphere which at $E80430kg$ is $E80377$ times the mass of our visible sphere. Table 2 establishes the similarity of Zybetspheres, regardless of their scale as defined by say $\textcircled{Z}M$. That there is an elegant uniformity of Zybetspheres from the smallest to the largest, and no matter what their ultimate $\textcircled{Z}M$ is, at some $\textcircled{Z}T$ in their evolution their parameters match the parameters of our visible sphere, within this Z_m range, and perhaps outside this range.

Graphing Table 2 parameters reveals that correlations are mostly log-log linear and with $R^2 = 1$ or ≈ 1 . Naturally correlations relating parameters of our Zybertsphere to measurable parameters draw interest and of special interest is $\textcircled{Z}\dot{Z}$ ($\Delta\textcircled{Z}/\Delta\textcircled{Z}T$) - the ZC equivalent of the Hubble Constant Redshift Drift. Table 2 shows that in Zybert Cosmology $\textcircled{Z}\dot{Z}$ correlates linearly with $\textcircled{Z}T$, so measuring $\textcircled{Z}\dot{Z}$ will identify the age of our Zybertsphere. Such simple elegant underlying inherently fundamental ZC correlations are profoundly revealing and of immense consequence and enormous importance in Zybert Cosmology. Of such momentous importance that to bestow them this eminent distinction the principal correlations for $\textcircled{Z}T$ $\textcircled{Z}M$ $\textcircled{Z}R$, based on $\textcircled{Z}\dot{Z}$, are now here named the Zybert Golden Correlations, defined as

$\textcircled{Z}T =$	$-1.0008*\textcircled{Z}\dot{Z} + 4.8372$	$R^2 = 1$	Eq. 1a
$\textcircled{Z}M =$	$1.0402*\textcircled{Z}T - 8.9637$	$R^2 = 0.9984$	Eq. 1b
$\textcircled{Z}R =$	$0.3333*\textcircled{Z}M + 2.3991$	$R^2 = 1$	Eq. 1c
$\Delta\textcircled{Z}A'/\Delta\textcircled{Z}T =$	$1.0003*\textcircled{Z}\dot{Z} - 21.67$	$R^2 = 1$	Eq. 1d
$\textcircled{Z}p =$	$-0.0719*\textcircled{Z}T^3 + 2.5125*\textcircled{Z}T^2 - 29.311*\textcircled{Z}T + 88.422$	$R^2 = 0.9972$	Eq. 1e
ΔT vs	$\textcircled{Z}T, \textcircled{Z}M, \textcircled{Z}R, \textcircled{Z}A, \textcircled{Z}V, \textcircled{Z}A', \textcircled{Z}Z, \textcircled{Z}p$ as polynomials	$R^2 = 1$	Eq. 1f

Most ZC parameters (as logarithms) have linear correlations and most correlations have $R^2=1$ or ≈ 1 . Although mostly linear, even non-linear correlations also have high Coefficients of Determination (R^2). But note, the constants in the correlation equations are approximate, being based on approximate data and simulations and interpolations. Eq. 1d to 1f are Auxiliary Zybert Golden Correlations demonstrating that correlations between various types of Zybertspheric parameters also correlate highly ($R^2>0.99$).